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***Improving Business Processes
with Blockchain:
Model-driven Generation
of Secure Smart Contract Code***

Technical Report

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Introduction

Second generation blockchains, such as Ethereum [1] and HyperLedger Fabric [2], provide a trusted environment to execute smart contracts, executable code whose outcome is predictable and not subject to corruption. Consequently, many organizations are considering implementing inter-organizational business processes – sets of inter-related activities aimed at achieving a common goal, which are often adopted to represent the obligations among different organizations – as smart contracts. When doing so, it is often incorrectly assumed that, because they run on a blockchain, smart contracts will by default address all security requirements. Smart contracts can be effective in enforcing some security requirements (e.g., non-repudiation), but they can also be detrimental for others (e.g., confidentiality). In addition, when multiple security requirements hold, determining to which extent a blockchain may address them becomes non-trivial.

This project aims at making use of model-driven engineering techniques to determine which real-world business processes would benefit from being implemented as smart contracts. To this aim, the project adopted SecBPMN2BC [3], a model-driven framework to generate smart contracts from business processes, which has been proposed by the applicant and other researchers and – to this day – is the only framework of this kind. More specifically, the project used SecBPMN2BC to model the security requirements that must be held for a business process, to determine which portions of the process should be run on a blockchain.

Background

SecBPMN2BC is a model-driven framework to support the development of blockchain-based applications. One of the prerequisites for this framework is that the application or parts of it can be represented as a business process, which in turn could be implemented as a business process. This assumption is justified by the fact that many information systems are process-aware [4], and that tools to execute business processes on a blockchain – either by translating it into smart contract code [5] or by interpreting the model at runtime [6] – have been proposed.

SecBPMN2BC is organized in four steps: Requirements Elicitation, On-chain Elements Identification, Model Revision, and Implementation

Requirements Elicitation

The first step takes as input an informal description of functional and security requirements for the application to be developed (e.g., as textual documentation), and produces a formal description of the application and its security requirements.

To support this step, SecBPMN2BC extends the SecBPMN language [7], which is in turn an extension of the Business Process Modeling Notation (BPMN) language commonly used to model business processes [8]. Compared to BPMN, SecBPMN2BC introduces annotations to represent security requirements, which can be attached to activities (units of work composing the process), data objects (information being consumed and/or produced by activities), and messages (information being exchanged between different organizations).

Auditability		Authenticity	
Availability		Integrity	
Non Repudiation		Separation of duties	
Bind of duties		Non Delegation	
Privity - public		Privity - user defined	
Privity - private		Privity - strong dynamic	
Privity - weak dynamic		Enforceability	
Enforceability - public		Enforceability - user defined	
Enforceability - public		On-chain (To be used on phases 2 and 3)	

Figure 1: Security annotations supported by SecBPMN2BC

An overview of the security annotations supported by SecBPMN2BC is shown in Figure 1. The reader should refer to [3] for further details.

On-chain Elements Identification

The second step takes as input the formal description of the application and its security requirements identified during the previous step and determines which elements of the application would benefit from being implemented as blockchain smart contracts. In addition, this step also identifies conflicting security requirements. As a result, the description is updated with this information.

To support this step, a set of enforcement rules, as well as an algorithm to identify the affected elements and to merge the rules, has been introduced. These components enrich the SecBPMN2BC model by annotating which process element should be implemented on a blockchain and how (e.g., storing data in unencrypted or encrypted form). The algorithm has been implemented as an Eclipse plugin. However, it lacks a graphical frontend to visually show the process model and the results of the reasoning. Once again, the reader should refer to [3] for further details.

Model Revision

This step is needed only if security conflicts are identified, or if the user disagrees with the decisions being made after the On-chain Elements Identification step. This step takes as input the SecBPMN2BC model annotated with on-chain elements, and it manually revises the security

requirements and/or the on-chain annotations. Then, the On-chain Elements Identification step is repeated to check if all conflicts are resolved.

Implementation

The final step takes as input the SecBPMN2BC model annotated with on-chain elements and produces the actual application. Currently, this step is entirely manual.

Project Structure

The first task being performed on the project was to identify, together with industry partners, real-world case studies that would be relevant to Fintech domain. The outcome of this task was two case studies: one on the handling of humanitarian tokens to assist people in need, the other on certifying the provenance of luxury items.

After identifying the case studies, the PI exploited SecBPMN2BC to create models describing some of the processes regulating the case studies, and to identify which portions of the process could be implemented on a blockchain.

Then, the industry partners validated the models to make sure that they reflected the requirements for the case studies, and that the decisions taken by SecBPMN2BC to implement process elements on a blockchain were consistent with the security requirements. The industry partners were also asked to indicate if some features they would have needed were missing from the tools supporting SecBPMN2BC.

Based on the input from the industry partners, the PI then identified which of the missing features were most relevant and could be addressed during the project's timeframe. Such features were then implemented in an extended version of the tools supporting SecBPMN2BC.

Finally, the PI asked the industry partners to validate the extended version of the tools by using them and providing feedback on their user experience.

The following sections of this report will discuss each task in the project in greater detail.

Case Studies Identification

This section will provide a description of the case studies being identified by the PI together with the industry partners. Both case studies aim at providing a blockchain-based platform making use of Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs). For each case study, the architecture of the solution, two use cases, and the security requirements have been analyzed.

Humanitarian Token Solution

Traditionally, humanitarian agencies are required to share the identity of people in need, together with other sensitive information about them, with external suppliers or financial service providers. This can bring privacy issues to those people.

To address this, Partisia (one of the industry partners involved in the project) together with the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) has designed a Humanitarian Token Solution (HTS) to give digital cash to people in need. Digital cash can then be spent by them without having to disclose their identity with anyone but the humanitarian organization.

The program begins with the humanitarian organization registering eligible individuals and issuing them digital tokens. These tokens are stored in secure digital wallets that can be accessed through a smartphone app or via physical QR-coded cards for recipients who lack access to smartphones. This dual approach ensures inclusivity, allowing even those without advanced technology to benefit from the system.

Once distributed, these tokens can be spent at participating local vendors within the HTS network. This allows beneficiaries to purchase goods and services of their choosing, shifting aid distribution from a supply-driven model to one that is demand-led. Vendors accepting tokens can redeem them through authorized cash agents supported by the humanitarian organization, ensuring liquidity and continuity in the system.

In addition to aiding registered beneficiaries, the HTS system allows community members who are not direct recipients of the humanitarian aids to join the ecosystem. These participants can transact with tokens within the network, expanding the program's reach while maintaining control over token circulation.

Architecture

The HTS solution is organized as a client-server architecture: from the client side we have an app running on a smartphone, which can be used by phone users to send and receive digital tokens. From the server side we have a proxy, which is responsible for securely handling information on the beneficiary, and a smart contract responsible for maintaining the token balance for each user and for transferring tokens.

Use Case 1.1: Receiving Tokens

Beneficiaries can receive tokens from the humanitarian organization. This is regulated by the following process. Firstly, the beneficiary must show his QR card, which is then scanned by the operator working at the humanitarian organization with an app running on his/her phone to extract from the QR the address of the beneficiary. The operator then specifies the amount to be transferred to the beneficiary and then issues a transaction to the backend component by specifying the address of the organization, the address of the beneficiary and the amount, and signing the transaction with the signing key of the organization. The backend component performs the transfer and produces a receipt which is sent to the operator.

Use Case 1.2: Spending Tokens

Beneficiaries can spend tokens by buying products or services from local vendors. This is regulated by the following process. Firstly, the beneficiary (QR card holder) must show his QR card, which is then scanned by the vendor (phone user) with an app running on his/her phone to extract from the QR the address of the beneficiary and its signing key, which is encrypted. The vendor then specifies the amount due and requests the beneficiary to type his own PIN code to authorize the purchase. Once the beneficiary has done so, the phone user sends to the backend component the address, the encrypted signing key, and the PIN code of the beneficiary. The phone user then issues a transaction to the backend component by specifying his/her address, the address of the beneficiary and the amount. The backend component firstly decrypts the

signing key of the beneficiary, then signs the transaction being issued with the decrypted signing key and finally performs the transfer and produces a receipt which is sent to the vendor.

Security Requirements

Regarding the security requirements for this case study, the address of each user should be disclosed only after a transaction goes through, without providing any information on the identity of the owner of that address. Similarly, signing keys and PIN codes should be known only to the platform and to their owner. Under no circumstances should be disclosed with anyone else. Instead, transactions and receipts should be publicly accessible to ensure transparency. It should also not be possible to alter them. Whenever a transaction is prepared, issued, and processed, the corresponding activities should be subject to integrity and non-repudiation. Activities that may require user interaction (e.g., reading the QR card) should be subject to availability.

Luxury Products Authentication System

High-quality luxury products are distinguished by the superior quality of materials used in their production, which contributes to their extended lifecycles, often lasting several years. This durability allows them to be reused and resold. However, the market for counterfeit luxury products is highly lucrative and poses significant challenges to the legitimate luxury industry. Counterfeit products, made with substandard materials, lack the durability of genuine luxury products, adversely affecting both the sale of new products and the resale market for pre-owned luxury goods.

The traditional methods for verifying the authenticity of luxury products have proven inadequate in combating counterfeiting. These systems often rely on manual, costly, and inefficient authentication processes. Typically, the most reliable way to ensure the authenticity of a luxury product is by purchasing directly from authorized retailers of specific luxury brands. At these retailers, verification experts use specialized equipment to authenticate pre-owned products. Despite these efforts, the complexity of verifying the authenticity of luxury products, combined with the prevalence of counterfeit products in circulation, means consumers remain at risk of purchasing counterfeit products, especially during trade-ins or when buying pre-owned products.

To address this, Dymaxion (one of the industry partners involved in the project) together with researchers from the Blockchain Analytics Group at University of Applied Sciences Upper Austria has designed an authentication system for luxury products (LogisticsBDT) that guarantees full traceability and transparency for the entire lifecycle of luxury products. To this aim, LogisticsBDT makes use of tokens to represent the luxury products and to keep track of their history and of the current owner.

LogisticsBDT allows manufacturers to register their brands. Then, whenever a new luxury product is manufactured, a manufacturer can request LogisticsBDT to mint a new token representing that product, including uniquely identifiable properties (e.g., the product serial number).

Then, whenever the product is purchased, either for the first time for a new product or for the subsequent times for a pre-owned one, the buyer can access the complete history of the product. The buyer can also verify if the conditions defined in the token reflect the ones of the actual product and, if not, propose an update. Once the purchase is complete, the new owner is registered, as well as updated information on the conditions of the product.

Architecture

LogisticsBDT is composed of four main application components, which are responsible for registering brands, minting new tokens, viewing tokens, and transferring tokens. Each component is implemented as a three-tier architecture: the presentation tier is implemented as a web application, the business logic tier as a python application and as a set of blockchain smart contracts, and the data tier as JSON documents stored on an InterPlanetary FileSystem (IPFS).

Use Case 2.1: Minting New Tokens

Vendors of luxury items can mint a new token whenever they manufacture a new product. This is regulated by the following process. Firstly, the manufacturer scans a QR code attached to the product with an app running on his/her phone and submits this information to the authentication system, which checks if a token for that product already exists. If so, it sends the product metadata to the manufacturer and the process ends. Otherwise, it asks the manufacturer to create metadata for the product (e.g., serial number, model, etc.). Once the manufacturer has created the metadata, he/she issues a transaction to the authentication system by specifying his/her address and the metadata and signing the transaction with his/her signing key. The backend component validates the transactions and produces a new token and receipt which is sent to the manufacturer.

Use Case 2.2: Transferring Tokens

Owners of a luxury product can sell their product to other users. This is regulated by the following process. Firstly, the seller scans the QR code attached to the product with an app running on his/her phone and submits this information to the authentication system, which retrieves the metadata associated with that product (including the id of the token representing that product) and sends them to the seller. The seller then issues a pending transaction by specifying the token and his own address, signs the transaction with his/her own signing key, and submits the pending transaction to the authentication system. The authentication system validates the transaction and generates a QR code for that transaction, which is then sent back to the seller and displayed on his/her phone. The buyer then scans the transaction QR code with an app running on his/her phone and submits this information to the authentication system, which retrieves the transaction and sends its metadata to the buyer. The buyer then assesses the transaction, verifies if he/she agrees with the transaction metadata (e.g., if the product being sold corresponds to the one described in the metadata), finalizes the transaction by signing it with his/her own signing key, and issues the transaction it to the authentication system. The authentication system validates the transaction and checks if the buyer agreed with the purchase. If so, it updates the product metadata by specifying the buyer as the new owner. Finally, it notifies the seller about the outcome of the sale.

Security Requirements

Regarding the security requirements for this case study, transactions and receipts should be publicly disclosed only for products that have never been sold, to ensure privacy for the owner. All the other information (purchase transactions, product metadata, signing keys) should be kept confidential and accessible only to the actors who need them.

Requirements Formalization

This section will provide a formalization for each use case identified in the two case studies. A SecBPMN2BC model capturing both functional and non-functional requirements have been created for each use case. Based on the outcome of the initial version of the tools supporting SecBPMN2BC (e.g., the tools available when the process started), the models also show which elements should be moved on a blockchain to maximize the enforcement of security requirements.

Use Case 1.1: Receiving Tokens

Figure 2: SecBPMN2BC model representing how a beneficiary receives token from a humanitarian organization.

Figure 2 shows the SecBPMN2BC model representing the process regulating how a beneficiary receives tokens from the humanitarian organization in the context of the humanitarian token solution case study. In particular, the tool suggests putting all the information being exchanged on a public blockchain to ensure transparency. To ensure confidentiality, the address and signing key of the sender should be encrypted, and only the digest of the address of the recipient should be stored. On the other hand, to ensure traceability, the amount, the transaction and the receipt should be unencrypted.

Concerning the activities composing the process, only activities Transfer tokens and Show outcome should be implemented as smart contracts. Indeed, Show QR card and Specify amount require human intervention, and cannot be automated. On the other hand, Read QR card and Request transfer could be automated, but they either produce or consume confidential information which should be decrypted before being manipulated by a smart contract.

Use Case 1.2: Spending Tokens

Figure 3: SecBPMN2BC model representing how a beneficiary spends tokens buying products or services from local vendors

Figure 3 shows the SecBPMN2BC model representing the process regulating how a beneficiary spends tokens buying products or services from local vendors in the context of the humanitarian token solution case study. In particular, the tool suggests putting all the information being exchanged on a public blockchain to ensure transparency. To ensure confidentiality, the address of the recipient, the PIN code and the signing key of the sender should be encrypted, and only the digest of the address of the sender should be stored. On the other hand, to ensure traceability, the amount, the transaction and the receipt should be unencrypted.

Concerning the activities composing the process, only activities Transfer tokens and Show outcome should be implemented as smart contracts. Indeed, Show QR card, Type PIN and Specify amount require human intervention, and cannot be automated. On the other hand, Read QR card, Receive PIN, Decrypt signing key, Sign transaction and Request transfer could be automated, but they either produce or consume confidential information which should be decrypted before being manipulated by a smart contract.

Use Case 2.1: Minting New Tokens

Figure 4: SecBPMN2BC model representing how a token for a new luxury product is minted by a manufacturer

Figure 4 shows the SecBPMN2BC model representing the process regulating how a token representing a new luxury product is minted by a manufacturer in the context of the luxury product authentication system case study. In particular, the tool suggests putting all the information being exchanged on a public blockchain to ensure transparency. To ensure confidentiality, the QR code and metadata of the new product should be encrypted, and only the digest of the signing key of the manufacturer should be stored. On the other hand, to ensure traceability, the transaction and the receipt should be unencrypted.

Concerning the activities composing the process, only activity Validate transaction should be implemented as a smart contract. Indeed, Show product QR code and Create product metadata require human intervention, and cannot be automated. On the other hand, Determine if product exists, Register product, and Send product metadata could be automated, but they either produce or consume confidential information which should be decrypted before being manipulated by a smart contract.

Use Case 2.2: Transferring Tokens

Figure 5: SecBPMN2BC model representing the the purchase of a product and the change of ownership of the corresponding token

Figure 5 shows the SecBPMN2BC model representing the process regulating the purchase of a product and the change of ownership of the corresponding token in the context of the luxury product authentication system case study. In particular, the tool suggests putting all the information being exchanged on a public blockchain to ensure transparency. However, to ensure confidentiality, all the information being exchanged should be encrypted or only the digest of it should be stored.

Concerning the activities composing the process, none of them should be implemented as a smart contract. Indeed, Show product QR code, Create transaction metadata, Scan transaction QR code and Assess transaction require human intervention, and cannot be automated. On the other hand, the other activities could be automated, but they either produce or consume confidential information which should be decrypted before being manipulated by a smart contract.

Initial Validation

To perform the initial validation, an interview was arranged with each industry partner. During the interview, the annotated SecBPMN2BC models for the case study provided by the industry partner were shown, as well as the procedure to produce them. The industry partner was then asked to comment on whether he agreed with the model, and if there was any feature lacking from the initial version of the tool that they would have liked to have.

Both partners thought that SecBPMN2BC was useful for capturing the actors involved in the process, the data exchanged, and the security constraints. They also agreed with the decisions made by SecBPMN2BC on which elements could be moved on a blockchain, and they found the tool to be useful to identify requirements and to validate the design of the architecture. On a couple of occasion, the tool suggested a design that was different from the one followed by the partners when implementing their solution, which could have provided an equal if not better enforcement of the security requirements.

Both authors suggested the following changes to be implemented to the tools supporting SecBPMN2BC:

1. Improving the user experience by making the tool easier to deploy and use. In particular, no graphical front-end was available in the original version of the tool, requiring the users to design the BPMN process model with external tools, manually extending the model with SecBPMN2BC-specific elements, and then running the tools.
2. Introducing ad-hoc profiles tailored to a specific blockchain implementation, rather than relying on the features common to all public or private blockchain implementations, when determining which process elements to implement on a blockchain.
3. Introducing mechanisms to forward-engineer smart contract code from SecBPMN2BC models, in order to semi-automatically obtain a working application from the model, thus automating the last step of the SecBPMN2BC framework.

Given the limited time and resources available for the project, the PI decided to focus on 1), leaving 2) and 3) as future work.

Implementation

Figure 6: Architecture of the extended version of SecBPMN2BC

Figure 6 shows the architecture of the extended version of SecBPMN2BC. A REST API was developed to expose the original implementation of the SecBPMN2BC reasoning algorithm. To do so, the Spring Boot framework was used, since the existing tools were implemented as an Eclipse Java application. In this way, it was possible to reuse the existing codebase.

For the visual editor, the PI decided to implement it as a web application, thus facilitating the deployment and use by interested parties. As a foundation, the PI chose to adopt bpmn-js¹, a well-established open-source JavaScript library to display and edit BPMN process models. bpmn-js allows us to introduce custom extensions to the BPMN language, thus making it possible to add SecBPMN2BC-specific elements. However, bpmn-js required a different approach to define extensions (custom properties) than the one originally adopted by the initial version of SecBPMN2BC (EMF metamodel extensions²). This caused models produced by the front-end to be incompatible with the ones being used by the original tools.

¹ See <https://bpmn.io/toolkit/bpmn-js/>

² See <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/modeling.emf.emf>

To make the original tools understand the models produced by the front-end, a set of rules to translate the models were defined, implemented through the Eclipse ATL framework³, and exposed as part of the REST API.

To facilitate the deployment of the new platform, Docker container files⁴ were created for the front-end and the back-end components (REST API, reasoning algorithm, model translator).

Final Validation

To validate the ease of use of the extended version of SecBPMN2BC, industry partners were asked to use the visual editor to create from scratch one of the processes identified by the case studies, to annotate an existing model with security requirements, and to run the algorithms to identify process portions to be implemented on a blockchain. While doing so, industry partners were asked to fill in a multiple-choice questionnaire.

Both industry partners found the visual editor easy to use for performing all tasks, despite having different levels of expertise on BPMN and on process modeling in general. They also expressed interest in having SecBPMN2BC available for them to use on future projects.

Conclusion

Both industry partners appreciated how the SecBPMN2BC approach allowed them to formalize the processes regulating their case studies and the security requirements.

In addition, the results provided by SecBPMN2BC were helpful for the industry partners in validating the blockchain-based applications they implemented as part of their case studies. Indeed, the results showed that their applications did not cause any security violation. In one case, the results also showed that, if their application had made more extensive use of the blockchain, it could have achieved higher enforcement of the security requirements.

Finally, the visual SecBPMN2BC editor that was developed during the project was found to be user friendly, intuitive and easy to use by the industry partners, who will continue to use it for future projects.

Deliverables

During this project, the following deliverables have been produced:

- A technical report discussing the evolution of the project and the outcomes (this document)
- A repository of process models created for the use cases identified from the case studies: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14508508>
- An online deployment of the extended SecBPMN2BC: <https://secbpmn2bc.compute.dtu.dk/>
- Source code of the extended SecBPMN2BC tools. At the time of writing, source code is not publicly available yet. Indeed, it is being reviewed by DTU Legal & Tech Transfer

³ See <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/modeling.mmt.atl>

⁴ See <https://www.docker.com/>

office. Once the review process is complete, source code will be published under Apache 2.0 license terms and it will become publicly available at <https://github.com/meronig/secbpmn2bc-online-editor>

- A questionnaire to evaluate the ease of use and usefulness of SecBPMN2BC for the Fintech industry: <https://forms.gle/CYBHSFjqziASC5Cv7>
- Answers to the above questionnaire: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/19DODOWRpDnzUCuu1mtuq8D_h9fJouOZnWGojrceRaxl/edit?usp=sharing

References

- [1] V. Buterin, “Ethereum white paper,” *GitHub Repos.*, vol. 1, pp. 22–23, 2013.
- [2] E. Androulaki *et al.*, “Hyperledger fabric: a distributed operating system for permissioned blockchains,” in *Proceedings of the Thirteenth EuroSys Conference*, Porto Portugal: ACM, Apr. 2018, pp. 1–15. doi: 10.1145/3190508.3190538.
- [3] J. Köpke, G. Meroni, and M. Salnitri, “Designing secure business processes for blockchains with SecBPMN2BC,” *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 141, pp. 382–398, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.future.2022.11.013.
- [4] M. Dumas, W. M. Van der Aalst, and A. H. Ter Hofstede, *Process-aware information systems: bridging people and software through process technology*. John Wiley & Sons, 2005. Accessed: Jan. 13, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://books.google.com/books?hl=it&lr=&id=isfGEAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR13&dq=process+aware+information+systems&ots=t33lqa78il&sig=_t5srsEMdjfLd8-68l7t0cwrPwo
- [5] O. López-Pintado, L. García-Bañuelos, M. Dumas, I. Weber, and A. Ponomarev, “Caterpillar: A business process execution engine on the Ethereum blockchain,” *Softw. Pract. Exp.*, vol. 49, no. 7, pp. 1162–1193, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1002/spe.2702.
- [6] A. B. Tran, Q. Lu, and I. Weber, “Lorikeet: A Model-Driven Engineering Tool for Blockchain-Based Business Process Execution and Asset Management.,” in *BPM (dissertation/demos/industry)*, 2018, pp. 56–60. Accessed: Jan. 13, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2196/BPM_2018_paper_12.pdf
- [7] M. Salnitri, F. Dalpiaz, and P. Giorgini, “Designing secure business processes with SecBPMN,” *Softw. Syst. Model.*, vol. 16, pp. 737–757, 2017.
- [8] M. Chinosi and A. Trombetta, “BPMN: An introduction to the standard,” *Comput. Stand. Interfaces*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 124–134, 2012.